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Page/s	Page 1 of 19

**ASSESSMENT OF NITRATE AND PHOSPHATE CONTENT OF FARM SOIL AND
GROUNDWATERS IN AN AGRI-MUNICIPALITY IN NUEVA VIZCAYA:
BASIS FOR MLGU RESTORATION EFFORTS AND
EUTROPHICATION CONTROL PROGRAM**

Lead Researcher: Elsa L. Cajucom, Ph.D.
Primary Collaborator: Gloria Vicky A. Antonio, MEd
Secondary Collaborator: Lorna C. Aban, MAEd
Research Assistants: Regidor L. Almendral
Michael S. Catacutan

ABSTRACT

Water safety and quality are essential, especially to human health, agriculture, aquaculture, industry, and all life forms. Effective crop production depends on an adequate supply of nutrients through fertilizer application to achieve maximum yield. However, farmers must manage soil nutrients appropriately to meet crops' fertility requirements without adversely affecting the quality of our valuable water resources. This research assessed the concentration of nitrates and phosphates in farmland soil and groundwater in the selected agro-ecosystem barangays in Dupax del Sur, Nueva Vizcaya, to ascertain the degree of anthropogenic influence via the application of fertilizer and other agro-chemicals to farmlands by farmers. Results show that the dissolved nitrate concentrations of both water sources and farmland soils for both barangays are below the recommended levels set by the respective standards referenced in the study - with the statistical analysis showing no statistically significant difference in nitrate concentration between both barangays. Also, data indicate that the soil phosphate concentrations on all sampled farmlands in both barangays are below the recommended levels set by the standards referenced in the study. However, the dissolved phosphate concentration in all sampled water sites is significantly above the recommended levels. The differences in soil and water phosphate concentrations can be due to having a separate irrigation source that has experienced multiple runoffs and leaching events, increasing its dissolved phosphate.

Keywords: *agrochemicals, biogeological processes, fertilizer application, sustainable farming*

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 2 of 19

INTRODUCTION

Rationale

Nueva Vizcaya is Cagayan Valley's vegetable capital and the country's next "salad bowl" (Department of Agriculture, 2011). In particular, Dupax del Sur is one of the leading vegetable producers. The income of most families is derived from rice farming, onion planting, and vegetable cultivation. Thus, it is inevitable for farmers to use fertilizers to boost crop yield. Farmers across the municipality use a variety of fertilizers to grow crops and to improve and increase the crop yield in every cropping season. Applying these inorganic fertilizers repeatedly for decades pollutes the soil and the water reservoir near it. If there is excessive use of fertilizers, it could potentially cause groundwater contamination.

Among the most pervasive pollutants of freshwater globally today are phosphate and nitrate (Khan & Ghouri, 2011). Sources of nitrates include runoff or seepage from fertilized lands, municipal and industrial wastewater, refuse dumps, animal feedlots, septic tanks, private sewage disposal systems, drainages, and decaying plant debris. Nitrates and phosphates are surplus nutrients that contaminate the soil and affect fertility.

Farmlands are the most common source of nitrates and phosphates (Lemma et al., 2017). Farmers are using organic fertilizers all year-round to boost their crop yields. Esteller et al. (2009) mentioned that this usage of organic wastes in agriculture may increase the production of crops by incorporating nutrients (such as nitrates and phosphates) into the soil. However, this could also lead to serious environmental concerns such as soil and water pollution, leaching, and eutrophication. Because nitrate can easily be transported from the soil into aquatic ecosystems by surface runoff and leaching, this causes groundwater contamination and aquatic eutrophication of surface waters (Guo et al., 2010). Moreover, according to Yeshno et al. (2019), the concentration of nitrates in soil often changes rapidly, on a timescale of hours to days, and are dictated by irrigation-precipitation pattern, fertilization and cultivation methods, plant uptake, and natural soil biochemical processes.

These nutrients are the main reason for water contamination and eutrophication, which could result from other phenomena that could seriously threaten the environment and its living organisms. Eutrophication happens when a body of water receives an excessive nutrient load, particularly phosphorus and nitrogen, resulting in an overgrowth of algae. This phenomenon often results in an overgrowth of algae. These algae will then cover the entirety of the surface of the water, keeping sunlight from penetrating. This will then cause some aquatic plants to die at the bottom of the water source. When these algae and aquatic plants die and decompose, oxygen is depleted from the water. This lack of oxygen in water causes the death of aquatic animals (Ghosh, 2021).

In the Philippines, there are limited studies about nitrate pollution and its environmental risks, such as groundwater pollution. The study of Bednarek et al. (2014)

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 3 of 19

shows that some of the groundwater sources sampled in a municipality in Laguna were found to be contaminated with nitrate-nitrogen from the use of inorganic nitrogen fertilizers, septic tanks, poor dug wells, and defective sewage systems. This became a significant concern that heightens fear in most communities because of the potential risks of groundwater pollution and the possible consequences it may bring depending on these water sources.

Although there is prior research about this issue in other locales, a study has yet to be conducted in the municipality of Dupax del Sur about the nitrate accumulation in farmlands and its subsequent environmental risks, such as groundwater contamination.

The lack of adequate research and studies regarding this matter in our country is alarming. Nitrates and phosphates pollution monitoring is needed to provide baseline data that can be used by decision-makers and policymakers for sustainable environmental management of river basins and aquatic ecosystems (Oremo et al., 2020).

The findings of the study will be beneficial for the environment and the community. Farmers will be aware of the potential risks of continued usage of inorganic or chemical fertilizers. Hence, they will be encouraged to use alternative fertilizers for more sustainable farming. Local governments could raise awareness about this phenomenon. This could encourage them to devise restoration efforts and formulate eutrophication control programs for affected areas. Lastly, the result of this study could be the basis for further environmental investigation on the excessive accumulation of nitrates and phosphates in soil and water reservoir. The researchers also believe that the study will help promote sustainable farming and is also aligned with risk reduction and mitigation, one of the components of SMU's Project WEALTH VERSION 2.0. This academic endeavor is also associated with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2, 6, 12, and 13. SDG2 is No hunger: End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture; SDG6 is Clean Water and Sanitation: Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all; SDG12 is Responsible Consumption and Production: Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns; and SDG13 is Climate Action: Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts (UN, n.d.).

Statement of the Problem

This study focused on the assessment of nitrate and phosphate concentrations in farm soil and irrigation water in Dupax del Sur, Nueva Vizcaya. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the nitrate concentration of the groundwater in different study sites?
2. What is the nitrate concentration of the farmland soil in different study sites?
3. What is the phosphate concentration of the groundwater in different study sites?
4. What is the phosphate concentration of the farmland soil in different study sites?

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 4 of 19

5. Is there a significant difference on the nitrate concentration in groundwater samples at different study sites?
6. Is there a significant difference on the nitrate concentration in farmland soil samples at different study sites?
7. Is there a significant difference on the phosphate concentration in groundwater samples at different study sites?
8. Is there a significant difference on the phosphate concentration in farmland samples at different study sites?
9. What recommendations in restoration efforts and eutrophication control programs may be proposed to the identified communities?

Statement of the Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference on the nitrate concentration in water samples at different study sites.
2. There is no significant difference on the nitrate concentration in soil samples at different study sites.
3. There is no significant difference on the phosphate concentration in water samples at different study sites.
4. There is no significant difference on the phosphate concentration in soil samples at different study sites.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-comparative research design to assess and compare the nitrate and phosphate concentrations of the farmland soil and ground waters in the two selected barangays in Dupax del Sur, Nueva Vizcaya.

Study Site and Sample Collection

Soil and water samples were collected from four farms, three of which are located in Barangay Mangayang and one in Gabut as shown in Figure 2.

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 5 of 19

Figure 2. Location of the Study Sites

Barangay Mangayang

Coordinates:

16.3089, 121.0731 (16° 19' North, 121° 4' East)

Estimated elevation above sea level:

376.9 meters (1,236.5 feet)

Barangay Gabut

Coordinates:

16.3252, 121.0660 (16° 20' North, 121° 4' East)

Estimated elevation above sea level

365.1 meters (1,197.8 feet)

Mangayang and Gabut Farmers' Profile

The farmers from Mangayang and Gabut are members of the Mangayang-Iñeangan-Duppes Irrigation Association, Inc. and Gabut Farmers Rice and Onion Growers Association, respectively. The farmlands cover an area from 0.8 hectares (8,000 sq. meters) to 1.5 hectares (15,000 sq. meters) with a mean area of 1.15 hectares (11,500 sq. meters). The common crop planted in Mangayang is sweet potato or commonly called camote. Rice is also grown on the two farms, while corn is on one farm. As one farmer shared, camote is a good alternative to rice since the profit is greater, considering the very low buying price of rice by traders. Vegetables such as tomato, pepper, Kentucky beans, string beans, winged bean (pallang), and bottle gourd (upo) are also planted as additional crops. The only farm visited in Gabut is planted with squash and red onions. To provide additional nutrients to the plants, all sampled farmers commonly use urea fertilizer, one of the most widely used chemical nitrogen fertilizers, according to Zhengzhou Huaqiang (2019). Triple 14 is another growth booster used. The name describes the NPK ratio present in the fertilizer, 14% nitrogen, 14% phosphorus, and 14% potassium. The remaining percent may include other nutrients the plants need (WhyFarmit, 2023). An average of six-seven bags of fertilizer are applied per hectare of farmland.

The plant growers are hesitant to use organic fertilizer, particularly the vermicompost given free by the Department of Agriculture. Vermicompost is the product of the decomposition process using various species of earthworms, which creates a mixture of decomposing vegetable or food waste, bedding materials, and vermicast (vermicompost, n.d.). From what the farmers experienced before, the worms which excrete the vermicast eventually destroyed their crops. For the entire year, the farmers have two cropping seasons or cycles. This is done to give time for the soil to sustain or restore its productivity. To augment their produce from the farms, one farmer has a piggery and another one takes care of ducks.

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 6 of 19

Water Sample Collection

Water samples were obtained from groundwater sources in the selected study sites. Each borehole was pumped for 3 minutes, and each sample bottle and its cap were rinsed three times with the well water during sampling. Water samples were placed in clean polyethylene bottles, were preserved with 1 mL sulfuric acid (96%, JT Baker) for every 500-mL water sample, and were stored in an icebox maintained at a temperature of about 4°C and were brought immediately to the laboratory for its nitrate-nitrogen determination.

Farm Soil Sample Collection

A manual collection method was used to collect soil samples in the study sites. This method was used primarily to collect surface and shallow subsurface soil samples. The surface was first removed from the sampling plot before collecting. In the sampling spot, a V-shaped cut to a depth of 15cm was made using a spade. Thick slices of soil from top to bottom of the exposed face of the 'V-shaped cut were placed in a clean container. The samples were mixed thoroughly, and foreign materials like roots, stones, pebbles, and gravel were removed. Then, the bulk was reduced by about half to one kilogram by quartering. Quartering was done by dividing the thoroughly mixed sample into four equal parts. The two opposite quarters were discarded, the remaining two quarters were remixed, and the process was repeated until the desired sample size was obtained. The collected samples were placed in a clean cloth of polyethylene bag. The bags were labeled with information like the spot's location and the collection date.

Data Gathering Procedure

1. Nitrate Assessment of Water and Farm Soil Samples

Nitrate concentration ($[\text{NO}_3\text{-N mg/L}]$) was determined using the ultraviolet spectrophotometric screening method (Eaton et al., 2005). For this method, water samples were analyzed using an Ultraviolet-Visible (UV-VIS) Spectrophotometer in the ultraviolet (UV) range at 220 nm and 275 nm wavelengths. Measurements at both wavelengths correct for possible interference by dissolved organic matter. Dissolved organic matter may be absorbed at 220 nm and 275 nm, while NO_3^- is only absorbed at 220 nm. The nitrate concentration was calculated by subtracting the absorbance at 275 nm from the absorbance at 220 nm and then comparing the corrected absorbance to a calibration curve developed using standards of known nitrate concentration (Eaton et al., 2005). For this analysis, the Biobase Spectrophotometer UV-1000 was used, and all measurements were read against distilled water set at zero absorbance as a blank. Fifty milliliters of field samples were filtered prior to UV-VIS analysis, and 1 mL of 1N HCl was added to minimize interference from dissolved organic matter. Each sample was analyzed using the UV-VIS spectrophotometer thrice, and the average absorbance was calculated. To prepare the calibration curve, a stock nitrate solution was made by diluting 0.7218 g of potassium nitrate previously dried at 105°C for 24 hours and was cooled in a desiccator to 1 L in a volumetric flask with distilled water.

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 7 of 19

The concentration of the stock solution is 100 mg NO₃ - N/L or one milliliter of the stock nitrate solution containing 100 µg of NO₃-N. Standards in the 0 to 7 mg NO₃-N/L were prepared by diluting the stock nitrate solution. These standards were treated and analyzed in the same manner as the samples. A linear relationship between absorption and NO₃-N mg/L, or a calibration curve, was developed and used to convert the absorbances measured for the samples to nitrate concentrations in units of mg NO₃-N/L.

First, the chloride concentration in the farm soil sample was determined, the chloride reading was divided by 10, and an amount of silver sulfate equivalent to the amount of chloride was added. Then (2-5) mL of the sample was taken in the centrifuge test tube, and the volume was completed to 10 mL with distilled water. The tube was centrifuged for 10 min until the solution was clear. Five mL of the clear solution was taken in a glass evaporating dish, put in a water bath, evaporated to dryness, and cooled. Then 1 mL of phenoldisulphonic acid was added after 10 min, then 10 mL of water was added and transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask and made alkaline by adding conc. NH₄OH, diluted to volume and mixed. Then the absorbance at 650 nm was measured using Visible Spectrophotometer and cuvette.

2. Phosphate Assessment of Water and Farm Soil Samples

In a 250 mL volumetric flask, 50 mL of distilled water was prepared, with 0.75 g of ammonium sulfate and 5 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid added. The solution was allowed to cool, as the heat was generated upon pouring the concentrated sulfuric acid, and then was diluted to the mark with distilled water.

For water samples, 10 mL of the sample and 200 mL of the ammonium sulfate solution were added to an Erlenmeyer flask and shaken occasionally over 30 minutes. The sample was filtered through filter paper to filter unwanted debris.

For farm soil samples, the obtained samples were oven-dried overnight at 50°C. 10 g of the dried soil samples and 200 mL of the ammonium sulfate solution were added to an Erlenmeyer flask and shaken occasionally for over 30 minutes. The sample was filtered through filter paper to remove any unwanted debris.

A standard solution was prepared by formulating a 300 mg/L stock solution by accurately weighing approximately 0.220g of solid potassium phosphate monobasic (KH₂PO₄) into a 500 mL volumetric flask and diluting it to the mark with distilled water. 10 mL of the stock solution was pipetted into a 200 mL, 250 mL, 500 mL, and 1L volumetric flask and diluted to the mark to obtain 15, 12, 6, and 3 mg/L standard solutions, respectively. 15 mL of the stock solution was pipetted into a 1L volumetric flask and diluted to mark to obtain a 4.5 mg/L solution.

Using 100 mL of distilled water, 5 g of ammonium molybdate was dissolved. Then, 160 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid was slowly added to the solution and diluted to 500 mL with distilled water. Into a 150 mL Erlenmeyer flask, 10 mL of each standard phosphate

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 8 of 19

solution was pipetted. 20 mL of distilled water, 2 mL of the molybdate solution, and a spatula of ascorbic acid crystals were added to the standard solution and heated slowly until boiling – resulting in a deep blue or green color. The solution was allowed to cool, and its absorbance reading was measured using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer at 650 nm. Into a 150 mL Erlenmeyer flask, 10 mL of each prepared sample solution was pipetted. 20 mL of distilled water, 2 mL of the molybdate solution, and a spatula of ascorbic acid crystals were added to the standard solution and were heated slowly until boiling. The solution was allowed to cool, and its absorbance reading was measured using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer at 650 nm.

Using the standard curve obtained from the absorbance readings of standard phosphate at known concentrations, an equation was obtained from the equation of its trendline using Microsoft Excel data processing software. The equation of the trendline was presented as $y=mx+b$, where y is the absorbance of the sample and x is the phosphate concentration of the sample. The measured absorbance readings of each sample were integrated into the equation, and the phosphate concentration was obtained by solving for x .

Treatment of Data

Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the nitrate and phosphate content of the samples tested in three replicates. The data were tested using a t-test to determine whether significant differences in the nitrate-nitrogen and phosphate concentrations of the farmland soils and groundwater sources at different study sites were present. The groundwater quality criteria used for interpreting the results were obtained from the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) Administrative Order No. 2016-08 for Class C waters and Nutrient Status Maps for both nitrogen and phosphorus content as of June 2017 in Nueva Vizcaya from the Department of Agriculture - Bureau of Soils and Water Management.

Ethical Considerations

This study was approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) at Saint Mary's University, Ponce Street, DMM, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, with a cellphone number: 09177053041 and email: reb@smu.edu.ph There is no conflict of interest in conducting this study. The study involved the conduct of laboratory procedures on the level of concentration of nitrate and phosphate in farm soil and irrigation water. It did not involve human or animal participants. Since the study dealt with chemicals, the researchers executed standard chemical practices to minimize the risk. Specially, these chemicals posed high-risk hazards to the environment, and non-carcinogenic health risks to laboratory users if accidentally exposed by skin contact, inhalation, or ingestion. The researchers are trained and well-equipped to handling these chemicals and other chemical agents used to analyze the levels of nitrate and phosphate concentration in water and soil samples. The CNS laboratory has an established Hazardous and Biological Waste

Document Code	URC-F0-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 9 of 19

Management Policy (2020). Lastly, all procedures where infectious/hazardous or possibly infectious aerosols/splashes created were conducted in biologically and chemically safe laboratory benches and/or stations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1. Nitrate Concentration

The absorbance readings at 220 nm and 275 nm were recorded in triplicates and averaged to calculate the corrected absorbance reading by finding the difference between the two readings. Table 1 displays the resulting absorbance readings of the standards.

Table 1. Concentrations and Absorbances of Nitrate Standard

Concentration (mg/L)	Absorbance (220 nm)				Absorbance (275 nm)				Corrected Absorbance (A220 - A275)
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Average	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Average	
0	0.229	0.188	0.171	0.196	0.004	0.012	0.000	0.005	0.191
1	0.401	0.399	0.406	0.402	0.053	0.056	0.057	0.055	0.347
2	0.628	0.622	0.621	0.624	0.055	0.053	0.053	0.054	0.570
3	0.826	0.830	0.828	0.828	0.054	0.054	0.053	0.054	0.774
4	1.026	1.023	1.023	1.024	0.052	0.050	0.052	0.051	0.973
5	1.203	1.204	1.190	1.199	0.051	0.049	0.052	0.051	1.148
6	1.373	1.370	1.358	1.367	0.052	0.053	0.053	0.053	1.314
7	1.654	1.607	1.588	1.616	0.053	0.053	0.048	0.051	1.565

Plotting the corrected absorbance readings of the standards on a graph yields a trendline, which determines the equation used to find the nitrate concentration of unknown samples. Figure 1 below shows the standard curve for determining the nitrate concentration in both water and farmland soil samples.

Figure 1. Standard Curve of Nitrate Concentration

The procedure for determining corrected absorbance for the nitrate standard is applied to the water and farmland soil samples collected from different labeled locations in Dupax del Sur.

A. Nitrate Concentrations of Water Samples

Tables 2 and 3 display the corrected absorbance readings and nitrate concentrations for the ground and irrigation water samples, respectively.

Table 2. Absorbance Readings of Water Samples for Nitrate Test

Location	Sample	Absorbance (220 nm)				Absorbance (275 nm)				Corrected Absorbance (A220 - A275)
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Ave	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Ave	
Brgy. Mangayang	MIWS-01	0.354	0.359	0.364	0.359	0.133	0.137	0.137	0.136	0.223
	MGWS-02 RICE	0.412	0.415	0.406	0.411	0.179	0.181	0.180	0.180	0.231
	MIWS-03 CAMOTE	0.333	0.329	0.331	0.331	0.127	0.125	0.126	0.126	0.205
	MIWS-04 MAIN	0.338	0.347	0.369	0.351	0.139	0.143	0.151	0.144	0.207
Brgy. Gabut	GIWS-01 MAIN	0.462	0.454	0.457	0.458	0.172	0.167	0.165	0.168	0.290
	GIWS-02	0.358	0.359	0.355	0.357	0.134	0.132	0.132	0.133	0.225

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 11 of 19

Table 3. Nitrate Concentrations of Water Samples

Location	Sample	Equation	Nitrate Concentration (mg/L)
Brgy. Mangayang	MIWS-01	$f(x) = 0.195x + 0.177$ where x is the Nitrate concentration and f(x) is the corrected absorbance	0.236
	MGWS-02 RICE		0.277
	MIWS-03 CAMOTE		0.144
	MIWS-04 MAIN		0.154
Brgy. Gabut	GIWS-01 MAIN		0.579
	GIWS-02		0.246

It is worth noting in Table 3 that GIWS-01 MAIN, irrigation water collected from Gabut, contains the most dissolved nitrate per liter of irrigation water. However, all water sites have dissolved nitrate levels that are significantly lower than the acceptable levels of class C waters based on DENR-AO No. 2016-08, which is 7 mg/L.

B. Nitrate Concentrations of Farmland Soil Samples

The corrected absorbance readings and nitrate concentrations for the farmland soil samples are presented in Tables 4 and 5, respectively.

Table 4. Absorbance Readings of Farmland Soil Samples for Nitrate Test

Location	Sample	Absorbance (220 nm)				Absorbance (275 nm)				Corrected Absorbance (A220 - A275)
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Ave	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Ave	
Brgy. Mangayang	MSS-01	3.696	3.699	3.701	3.699	3.398	3.398	3.398	3.398	0.301
	MSS-02	3.523	3.523	3.523	3.523	3.301	3.301	3.301	3.301	0.222
	MSS-03	3.620	3.622	3.622	3.621	3.385	3.386	3.388	3.386	0.235
	MSS-04	3.549	3.550	3.549	3.549	3.101	3.103	3.100	3.101	0.448
	MSS-05	3.613	3.611	3.611	3.612	3.370	3.371	3.371	3.371	0.241
Brgy. Gabut	GSS-01	3.319	3.315	3.317	3.317	3.088	3.085	3.089	3.087	0.23
	GSS-02	3.566	3.570	3.566	3.567	3.322	3.322	3.320	3.321	0.246

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 12 of 19

Table 5. Nitrate Concentrations of Farmland Soil Samples

Location	Sample	Equation	Nitrate Concentration (mg/kg)
Brgy. Mangayang	MSS-01	$f(x) = 0.195x + 0.177$ where x is the Nitrate concentration and f(x) is the corrected absorbance	0.636
	MSS-02		0.231
	MSS-03		0.297
	MSS-04		1.390
	MSS-05		0.328
Brgy. Gabut	GSS-01		0.272
	GSS-02		0.354

It is also worth noting in Table 5 that MSS-04 has the highest soil nitrate concentration among the farmland soil samples obtained. However, all soil samples fall significantly below the acceptable levels of nitrate in the soil, which is 10-50 mg/kg (HORIBA Instruments Singapore, 2015).

Section 2. Phosphate Concentration

Table 6 shows the absorbance readings of the phosphate standard at 650 nm.

Table 6. Concentrations and Absorbances of Phosphate Standard

Concentration (mg/L)	Absorbance (650 nm)			
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Average
0	0.056	0.050	0.047	0.051
3	0.095	0.098	0.096	0.096
4.5	0.128	0.122	0.128	0.126
6	0.167	0.170	0.165	0.167
12	0.202	0.205	0.202	0.203
15	0.243	0.240	0.248	0.244

A standard curve is constructed based on the absorbance readings of the phosphate standard. The equation of the trendline was used in determining the phosphate

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 13 of 19

concentration of unknown samples. Figure 2 illustrates the standard curve obtained from the phosphate standard.

Figure 1. Standard Curve of Phosphate Standard

The procedure for determining the absorbance phosphate standard was applied to the water and farmland soil samples collected from different identified sites in Dupax del Sur.

A. Phosphate Concentrations of Water Samples

Tables 7 and 8 display the absorbance readings at 650 nm and phosphate concentrations for each of the ground and irrigation water samples, respectively.

Table 7. Absorbance Readings of Water Samples for Phosphate Test

Location	Sample	Absorbance (650 nm)			
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Average
Brgy. Mangayang	MIWS-01	0.083	0.083	0.082	0.083
	MGWS-02 RICE	0.087	0.088	0.087	0.087
	MIWS-03 CAMOTE	0.089	0.087	0.089	0.088
	MIWS-04 MAIN	0.082	0.083	0.082	0.082
Brgy. Gabut	GIWS-01 MAIN	0.087	0.088	0.087	0.087
	GIWS-02	0.081	0.083	0.081	0.082

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 14 of 19

Table 8. Phosphate Concentrations of Water Samples

Location	Sample	Equation	Phosphate Concentration (mg/L)
Brgy. Mangayang	MIWS-01	$f(x) = 0.012x + 0.066$	1.416
	MGWS-02 RICE	where x is the phosphate concentration and f(x) is absorbance	1.75
	MIWS-03 CAMOTE		1.833
	MIWS-04 MAIN		1.333
Brgy. Gabut	GIWS-01 MAIN		1.75
	GIWS-02	1.333	

It is worth noting in Table 8 that MIWS-03 CAMOTE, groundwater sample from Mangayang, contains the most dissolved phosphate per liter of irrigation water. However, all water samples sites have dissolved phosphate levels that are higher than the acceptable levels of class C waters based on DENR-AO No. 2016-08, which is 0.5 mg/L.

B. Phosphate Concentrations of Farmland Soil Samples

Tables 9 and 10 show the absorbance readings at 650 nm and phosphate concentrations for each of the farmland soil samples, respectively.

Table 9: Absorbance Readings of Farmland Soil Samples for Phosphate Test

Location	Sample	Absorbance (650 nm)			
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Average
Brgy. Mangayang	MSS-01	0.107	0.075	0.080	0.087
	MSS-02	0.118	0.122	0.152	0.131
	MSS-03	0.102	0.136	0.109	0.116
	MSS-04	0.128	0.158	0.129	0.138
	MSS-05	0.073	0.074	0.076	0.074
Brgy. Gabut	GSS-01	0.089	0.087	0.118	0.098
	GSS-02	0.229	0.229	0.226	0.228

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 15 of 19

Table 10: Phosphate Concentrations of Farmland Soil Samples

Location	Sample	Equation	Phosphate Concentration (mg/kg)
Brgy. Mangayang	MSS-01	$f(x) = 0.012x + 0.066$	1.75
	MSS-02	where x is the phosphate concentration and f(x) is absorbance	5.42
	MSS-03		4.16
	MSS-04		6.0
	MSS-05		0.6
Brgy. Gabut	GSS-01		2.6
	GSS-02	13.5	

GSS-02 has the most phosphate present in its farmland soil among the farmland sites the samples are obtained from. Meanwhile, MSS-02 obtained the highest phosphate concentration among farmland sites in Brgy. Mangayang may be attributed to the presence of piggery and duck poultry. However, all farmland sites exhibit phosphate levels below the recommended amount which is 25 to 50 mg/kg.

Section 3. Comparisons of Nitrate and Phosphate Concentrations

Table 11. T-test Results for Nitrate and Phosphate Concentrations of the Water Samples in the two Barangays

Concentration in Water Sample	Site	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Nitrate	Mangayang	4	.20275	.064412	-1.237	1.076	.422
	Gabut	2	.41250	.235467			
Phosphate	Mangayang	4	1.5830	.24548	.185	4	.862
	Gabut	2	1.5415	.29486			

The t-test results in Table 11 show that the nitrate and phosphate concentrations of the water samples obtained from the different irrigation sites in Barangays Mangayang and Gabut are not significantly different from each other with p-values greater than 0.05.

Table 12. T-test Results for Nitrate and Phosphate Concentrations of the Soil Samples in the two Barangays

Concentration in Soil Sample	Site	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t (df = 5)	Sig. (2-tailed)
Nitrate	Mangayang	5	.57640	.480772	.731	.498
	Gabut	2	.31300	.057983		
Phosphate	Mangayang	5	6.1660	4.41296	1.365	.230
	Gabut	2	1.6000	1.41421		

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 16 of 19

Table 12 reflects the t-test results which indicate that the nitrate and phosphate concentrations in the different soil samples gathered in Barangays Mangayang and Gabut are not significantly different from each other with p-values greater than 0.05

The different nitrate and phosphate concentrations were compared with the acceptable levels. Tables 13 and 14 show the one-sample t-test results for the water and soil samples, respectively.

Table 13. One-sample t-test results on the water samples

Sample	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Test value	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
NitrateW	6	.27267	.159092	7	-103.579	5	.000	-6.727333
PhosphateW	6	1.5692	.23239	0.5	11.270	5	.000	1.06917

The results in Table 13 indicate that the mean nitrate concentration of the six water samples of .27 mg/L is significantly lower than the recommended level of 7 mg/L ($p < .001$). While the mean phosphate concentration of 1.57 mg/L is significantly higher than the acceptable level of 0.5 mg/L ($p < .001$).

Table 14. One-sample t-test on the soil samples

Sample	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Test value	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
NitrateS	7	.50114	.413731	25	-156.667	6	.000	-24.498857
PhosphateS	7	4.8614	4.27551	25	-12.462	6	.000	-20.13857

Table 14 reflects the results indicating that the mean nitrate concentration of the seven soil samples of .50 mg/kg is significantly lower than the recommended level of 25 mg/kg ($p < .001$). While the mean phosphate concentration of 4.86 mg/L is significantly higher than the acceptable level of 0.5 mg/L ($p < .001$).

The nutrient status map by the Bureau of Soils and Water Management of the Department of Agriculture (2017) shows low to moderately low dissolved nitrogen levels in Dupax, Nueva Vizcaya farm soils, consistent with the findings of the study. Although nitrates are more soluble in water and can leach towards groundwater or irrigation water, the low levels of dissolvable nitrate and clay-loam soil in Dupax del Sur limit the amount of leached nitrates in irrigation water, which mainly consist of dissolved nitrates from organic matter that were minimized during analysis (Geisseler & Horwath, 2016).

On the other hand, the nutrient status map by the Bureau of Soils and Water Management of the Department of Agriculture (2017) shows varying but mostly low levels

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 17 of 19

of dissolved soil phosphorus in Dupax, Nueva Vizcaya, consistent with the study results. Despite the low phosphate concentration in farmland soil, the study found high levels of dissolved phosphate in irrigation water in some areas of Dupax del Sur, which could be caused by multiple farmland surface runoff events that have occurred – resulting in low dissolved phosphate in the soil but high dissolved phosphate in groundwater (Chakraborty, 2022).

CONCLUSIONS

The study found that the dissolved nitrate concentrations in both irrigation water sources and farmland soils for both barangays were below recommended levels, with no statistically significant difference. It can be concluded that nitrates from the soil obtained from the two communities are nearly depleted, and there are low amounts of nitrate that can be leached through various water sources - leading to low concentrations of dissolved nitrate in the irrigation water as well. Soil phosphate concentrations in all sampled farmlands were below recommended levels, but dissolved phosphate concentrations in all sampled irrigation water sites were significantly above recommended. The differences in soil and water phosphate concentrations may be due to a separate irrigation source experiencing multiple runoffs and leaching events, increasing its dissolved phosphate.

RECOMMENDATIONS

IEC leaflet materials can be conceptualized and designed to inform the target communities of soil and water management towards green and sustainable farming. Also, it is recommended to sample more irrigation and farmland sites and modify procedures to minimize dissolved organic matter interference. Obtaining multiple samples from different parts of each site can provide multiple observations for each, allowing for additional statistical analyses to improve the findings' reliability further.

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Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 18 of 19

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Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 19 of 19

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